
FACTORS INFLUENCING THE INVOLVEMENT OF THE TEMPORARY EMPLOYEES: A STUDY BASED ON SELECTED PUBLIC SECTOR UNDERTAKINGS

Dr Amitava Basu¹, Dr.SouvikDutta²

¹ Associate Professor of Commerce, B.B. College, Asansol, West Bengal, India

² Department of Business Administration, B.B. College, Asansol, West Bengal, India

Abstract:

Employees' commitment can help in overall development of an organization. Alternatively, their non-involvement can put it into a deep trouble. The present era of globalization has given birth to different categories of non-payroll employees. They are normally hired for short term employment purposes that come to an end with the attainment of same. This type of contingent assignment may lead to their non-involvement in work processes and positive turnover intentions. Here, in our present study, we have tried to identify several factors using factor analysis that might be behind in this relation. In this regard, we have considered a group of temporary employees of different selected Public Sector Undertakings.

Keywords: *Employees' Commitment; Non-Involvement; Globalization; Work-Process; Attainment; Contingent.*

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1. Introduction

Employees are considered as one of the most important determinant and leading factors for attaining sustainable development of an organization. For that reason, any investment, in this regard, is normally considered as good investment. In this present era of competition and liberalization, it can directly contribute towards success of an organization. This is especially true not only in the service sector but also in manufacturing sector as well. In this way the important objective of retaining existing competent people of modern Human Resource Management practice may be badly affected.

Presently it has become a general practice in the organizations to offer various temporary employments to their prospective employees instead of offering permanent employment for instant fulfilment of their purposes. At present, the temporary workforce is a small but going to increase in proportion of the labour market in most of the industrialized countries like India as well where problem lies in unemployment and huge population outburst. The growth of the temporary work industry has undoubtedly become one of the most influential employment trends

of the last two decades (Connelly and Gallagher, 2006; Walsh and Decry, 2006). The temporary workforce is a small but increasing proportion of the labour market in most of the industrialized countries like India as well.

Undoubtedly, some benefits (such as minimization of employee hiring cost, saving of time etc.) are available in such type of employment but there is some problems as well. The major problem lies in the areas of job satisfaction, job involvement, organisational commitment and their work - attitude as a whole. Lot of researches has been done with the work attitude related areas of permanent employees but little has been done with the temporarily engaged employees (W. D. Robert and Helena D. Cooper – Thomas, 2009).

2. Objective of the Study

A large number of researches have examined the commitment related matter of permanent employees but little has done in this regard of temporary assignment. (Connelly, Gallagher, and Gilley, 2007; Gallagher and McLean Parks, 2001; Liden et al, 2003; Van Brucgel, Van Olffen and Olie, 2005). So, our foremost objective will be to identify the different influential factors might be behind positive or negative job involvement of temporary employees here.

3. Related Review of Literature

Saari and Judge (2004) have written that the most focal employee attitude is job satisfaction. Quinn (1985) has reported that more than five thousand articles have been published on job satisfaction. Bell and Weaver (1987) have mentioned in their literature that till the concept of job satisfaction is still worth exploring and controversial. Whereas Locke (1983) has commented that much of the literature is inconclusive in nature and debatable. Glisson and Durick (1988) have written that it is important to understand certain job characteristics such as skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy and feedback and how they affect behavioural outcomes in different ways. In a study conducted by Edet in 2008 shows that there is a genuine relationship between non – monetary compensation and work – related attitude when taken individually. Deci and et al (2001) have written that after taking a careful review of literature it appears that most of the research has been conducted to investigate some specific things like job attributes, role of manager and impact of personality dimensions on job satisfaction in the organizations based in the developing countries like India. Lincoln and Kalleberg (1990) have argued that the rewards offered by an organization may have a powerful effect on employees' work related attitude. Rahiman and Kodikal (2017) have investigated different facets of employee-attitude and its impact on their overall performance. Another study was undertaken by Annink and others (2015) to identify the factors that create work-family conflicts.

Although, job satisfaction has received most of the attention of all work – related attitudes, organizational commitment has become increasingly recognized in the organizational behaviour literature. Whereas job satisfaction is mainly concerned with the employee's attitude toward the job and the commitment is at the level of organization, a strong relationship between job satisfaction and organizational commitment has been found over the years as it has mentioned by Locke and Latham and et.al. in 1993. O'Drisol and Randall in 1999 have mentioned that extrinsic rewards are strongly associated with continuance commitment and intrinsic rewards are

strongly associated with job involvement and affective commitment. Lesabe and Nkosi (2007) have written that employee commitment has an impact on overall functioning of organizations in their literature. Whereas some observers like Carson, K., Carson, P., Roe, C., Birkenmeier, and Philips felt that organizational commitment is a dead issue because of the new environment and should be replaced by career commitment. Jiang and Klein (2001) have mentioned that high employee commitment is a prominent feature of world class organizations. But, unfortunately, even the best – performing organizations do experience turnover, lack of job – satisfaction and commitment related problems. In a recent study by Kodikal and others (2016) have studied the influence of QWL on organizational commitment and identified a positive relationship between these two. Research exposure on job involvement is comparatively of recent phenomena in the field of organizational psychology. Alternatively, the term job involvement has been discussed by Mckelvey and Sekaran (1977) as the merging of a person’s ego identity with his or her job. In a study conducted by Pathak, R. D., in 1977, utilizing a sample of 150 bank officers from four major public sector banks in India was investigated the inter – relationship between job involvement and need satisfaction. Morrow in 1983 has written that there is a positive relationship between job involvement and organizational commitment. Kanungo in 1982 has identified the relationship between job involvement and other numerous variables like job characteristics, performance, turnover and absenteeism. Walia (2015) has mentioned that job stress should be minimized for increasing an individual job involvement.

4. Research Methodology

Lot of elements or factors (Communication, information, voice, welfare, equality, recognition, pay, promotion, autonomy, role stressors, job specific training, size of the organization, responsibility, feeling of achievement, relationship between subordinate and peers, workload, meaningfulness, QWL, morale, accountability, leadership, CSR paid training and tuition reimbursement , company policy and administration, interesting job, treatment, employment alternatives, job scope, job tenure, job level, mutual trust, job involvement, turnover, job performance, respect attached with the job, education, organizational dependency, job esteem, attitude of the family and friends, age, supervisor’s Support, working hours, staffroom environment, leave and its sanctioning process, academic achievements, library facility and self-control), we have identified in this purpose of work – attitude. But there is a chance of creating problem, in handling, that much elements. For removing that problem and identification of important factors or elements that normally creates difference, in terms of employee – attitude following KMO method of Factor Analysis.

5. Findings and Discussion

KMO and Bartlett's Test of Temporary Employees

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.819
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	3.534E3
	Df	1081
	Sig.	.000

Here, we can interpret this outcome, of KMO, as ‘Great’ as it is being identified by Hutcheson and Sofroniou (1999; pp. 224 - 225). This interpretation has been done according to a rule of

thumb, introduced by them, in this context. They have categorized different values in the following manner - the values between 0.50 - 0.69 – Mediocre, 0.70 - 0.79 - Good, 0.80 - 0.89 - Great and above 0.90 - Superb, etc. Further, sig. value (.000), that we have got here, has also appeared as favourable for conducting factor analysis.

Rotated Component Matrix of Temporary Employees

	Component													
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
VAR00020	.684	.010	-.068	-.095	.051	.245	.029	-.072	.145	-.128	.113	-.177	-.121	-.015
VAR00045	-.617	.125	-.198	-.127	.077	.017	-.046	-.073	-.018	-.051	.073	.042	.029	-.168
VAR00016	.456	-.074	.201	.197	.205	.005	-.030	.209	.129	.160	.178	.266	-.052	-.231
VAR00032	.454	.275	.184	.225	-.052	-.016	.174	-.008	.220	.137	.057	.115	.098	-.093
VAR00033	-.454	.003	-.237	-.098	-.057	.169	-.173	.072	-.204	-.068	-.435	-.121	-.063	-.115
VAR00039	-.444	-.186	-.018	-.092	.034	-.060	-.106	-.365	-.027	-.123	.160	-.095	.178	.058
VAR00019	.048	.621	.072	-.040	.090	.016	-.057	.055	.146	.121	.057	.064	.100	-.046
VAR00035	-.090	.567	-.045	.174	.217	.227	.117	-.050	-.002	.077	-.193	-.040	.057	.081
VAR00002	.056	.505	-.055	.186	.111	.010	.268	.180	-.055	-.102	.390	-.153	-.081	.085
VAR00017	.302	.467	.097	.247	-.046	.005	.137	.206	-.287	.135	.005	.174	.048	-.178
VAR00043	-.053	.447	.245	-.057	-.068	.223	-.020	.010	.189	-.071	.234	.412	-.139	.015
VAR00023	-.173	.439	.185	.054	.368	.179	.119	-.090	.195	.213	.043	.022	-.044	-.010
VAR00026	.134	.061	.686	.177	.015	.117	-.029	.021	.037	.071	.090	.185	.027	-.053
VAR00013	.226	.047	.469	.177	.087	.130	.195	.250	.200	.024	.147	-.192	-.242	-.013
VAR00007	.022	.154	.465	-.146	.299	.088	.020	.158	.089	.415	-.018	-.067	-.087	.073
VAR00028	.214	.205	.428	.162	.023	.224	.317	.102	-.002	.136	-.250	-.150	.068	.037
VAR00014	.173	.027	.428	.421	.133	.084	.083	.255	.110	-.145	-.012	-.108	-.053	-.162
VAR00024	.044	-.005	.064	.617	.025	.266	.052	.132	.103	.130	.016	-.033	.107	-.013
VAR00006	.220	.205	.101	.601	.059	-.041	-.054	-.106	.121	.061	-.006	-.009	-.154	.083
VAR00012	.024	-.070	.234	.467	.253	.183	.111	-.011	.158	.169	.111	.058	.139	.004
VAR00004	-.084	.219	-.018	.461	-.012	.213	.285	.033	.099	-.190	.138	.158	-.234	-.049
VAR00044	-.054	.154	-.058	-.012	.658	-.044	-.218	-.087	-.120	.005	.026	-.055	.153	.038
VAR00046	.065	.053	-.043	.341	.621	.076	.090	-.031	-.112	.069	-.094	.148	.048	.065
VAR00003	.004	.112	.235	-.079	.602	.090	.135	-.020	.262	.048	-.040	-.095	-.075	-.180
VAR00021	.050	.012	.244	.257	.389	.293	.125	.174	-.010	.113	.189	.093	-.181	-.013
VAR00025	.215	.225	-.248	.048	.325	.277	.288	.113	.189	.040	-.134	.293	-.087	.041
VAR00018	-.124	-.169	.139	.161	.315	.301	.291	.128	.296	-.018	.245	.024	-.042	.106
VAR00001	-.036	.094	.137	.118	.138	.666	.296	-.110	.044	-.008	.081	.085	.071	-.093
VAR00010	.181	.221	.147	.233	.067	.641	-.028	.123	.027	.142	.063	.151	.064	.039
VAR00015	.097	.061	.042	.145	-.011	.502	-.090	.282	.322	.184	.142	-.098	-.043	-.035
VAR00011	.090	.040	-.008	.033	.027	.053	.776	.094	.075	.008	-.055	.121	-.062	-.116
VAR00009	.257	.140	.321	.071	-.038	.134	.499	.023	.179	.111	.153	-.049	.233	.014
VAR00030	-.055	.193	.061	.191	.072	.151	.382	.046	-.321	.341	.358	-.048	-.053	.196
VAR00037	-.124	.102	.026	.066	-.054	.131	.119	.771	.063	.094	.113	-.050	.097	.100
VAR00038	-.236	.030	-.275	.113	.006	.019	.053	-.577	.011	.188	.001	-.132	.159	-.142
VAR00027	.228	-.074	-.027	.214	-.085	-.063	.287	.414	.257	.187	.223	.100	.057	-.185
VAR00029	.066	.037	.063	.138	-.096	.206	.145	.054	.590	.016	.235	.103	.077	-.060

VAR00031	.251	.224	.131	.158	-.007	.145	-.027	-.036	.556	.082	-.153	.080	-.119	.132
VAR00036	-.235	-.120	-.047	-.206	-.229	.150	-.162	-.255	-.505	-.048	.059	-.018	.001	-.037
VAR00022	.028	.123	-.003	.177	.011	.041	.031	.025	.101	.776	-.045	.065	-.164	.006
VAR00005	.190	.117	.234	-.031	.268	.277	.060	-.004	-.063	.549	.057	.142	.277	-.039
VAR00034	.017	.038	.033	.017	-.051	.167	-.052	.084	.036	-.020	.742	.001	-.033	-.064
VAR00042	-.034	-.001	-.035	-.014	.018	-.042	-.063	-.093	-.082	-.122	-.010	-.743	.004	.065
VAR00040	-.157	.134	-.095	.037	.141	.084	.103	-.233	-.064	-.123	-.068	.521	.055	.420
VAR00047	-.121	.187	-.203	-.073	.144	.159	.066	.079	-.054	-.058	.061	.023	.723	-.084
VAR00008	.072	.113	-.297	-.087	.094	.124	.127	.174	-.090	.110	.243	.061	-.551	-.153
VAR00041	.093	-.037	-.018	.001	-.032	-.059	-.104	-.149	.049	.041	-.008	-.018	-.007	.826

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 44 iterations.

- 1) **Enjoyment at Work:** Here under this factor, 'accountability', turnover and work-load are the three elements that have come out positive. It may be because of their terms of employment. Apart from that, the elements like job involvement, attitude of the family and friends have appeared negative to them. So they can't enjoy their work.
- 2) **Impression of the Job:** Under this factor, all the elements, such as, morale, respect attached with the job among others, information sharing, meaningfulness, staffroom environment and paid training and tuition reimbursement have come out as negative to the temporary work-life of the employees of selected PSUs currently under consideration and that's why, to them, impression of their job is also negative.
- 3) **Return from the Job:** Here also all the elements, namely, feeling of achievement, responsibility, staffroom environment, pay and contingent pay, job scope and equitable treatment have come out in negative interpretation. So, we can further say that the temporary employees are mostly dissatisfied with the return from their job.
- 4) **Look of the Organization:** Under this factor, temporary employees are dissatisfied with company policy and administration and recognition and satisfied with employee welfare and size of the organization. So, we can say 'look of their organization' is 'moderately' friendly to them.
- 5) **Expectations from the job:** Elements like Leave and its sanctioning process, library facility, voice, leadership style QWL and interesting job have got a place under this factor for temporary employees and we further say that their expectation from their job remains unfulfilled.
- 6) **Scope of individual satisfaction:** The temporary employees' of selected PSUs get a very limited scope of individual satisfaction at work. That might be considered significant reason behind merging of different elements like QWL, job stress and relationship with subordinate and peers under this factor for them.
- 7) **Scope of development:** The temporary employees get a little scope of development at work. So different elements, like, job – specific training, autonomy and job level have taken place under this factor for them.

- 8) **Involvement at work:** We have already discussed that these employees are totally dissatisfied with the organizational inputs offered to them by their organization. As a result of that, it has made them negatively involved at work. Under this factor, different elements, like, inequality, organizational dependency and job esteem (in negative sense) and employment alternative (in positive sense) can be seen here.
- 9) **Intra – organizational relationship:** Under this factor three elements - job tenure, mutual trust and education have come out as relevant to the temporary work-life of the employees of selected public undertakings in this regard.
- 10) **Corporate citizenship behaviour:** Here in this context, the CSR initiative of present organization has made them happy and unequal or individual treatment has made them unhappy here.
- 11) **Flexibility at work:** Two elements - working hours and age can be seen, in negative interpretation, under this factor and thereby they get very little flexibility at work.
- 12) **Requirement from the job:** Their requirement from their work remains untouched and that makes negatively committed towards their job and their organization. Under this factor, self-control is externally controlled to them.
- 13) **Motivation:** In this assignment they hardly get any scope for promotion and that makes them de-motivated at work.
- 14) **Organizational support system:** Organizational support to them is adequate to them as they don't get proper support from their supervisor or other senior person in their organization.

6. Conclusion

The study revealed that the factors we have identified are influential in a temporary work life. But, despite the several negative outcomes, practice of engaging temporary employees, from contractors and indirect sources, are still largely practiced across nations and industries, in different occupations, in different categories, such as, skilled, semi-skilled and unskilled. But considering them in diverse activities, providing them some sort of information about the organization, involving them in organizational decision making process, recognition for the good work done by them, employee friendly company policy and administration, democratic leadership style, proper working environment, consideration for training, equal treatment, enlarging their area of functioning, creating a sense of organizational dependency, flexible work – time, paid annual leaves and medical leave, an equipped staffroom, encouraging for further education, performance based pay, etc. might be considered, for them, and can be provided, to them, with a very little problems. Later on, that may appear helpful, in increasing, their morale, positive involvement and commitment with less turnover intentions.

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*Corresponding author.

E-mail address: Mailid:naac.hec@ gmail.co/souvik_bwn2003@ yahoo.co.in